

wingless-type MMTV integration site family, member 6 / Wnt family member 6 (WNT6) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : WNT6 belongs to the WNT gene family and encode secreted glycoproteins that are involved in short-range signaling during embryonic patterning. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of WNT6, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: WNT6, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

^{*}ML dicoveries of WNT6 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. wingless-type MMTV integration site family, member 6 / Wnt family member 6 (WNT6)

The mammary tumor-associated proto-oncogene WNT-1/INT-1 encoded a secreted protein implicated in the regulation of neural development in vertebrates and segmental pattern in *Drosophila*. Using a PCR-based strategy, Gavin et al. [14] isolated cDNAs encoding six novel, related proteins that were expressed in fetal mice. Predicted proteins were of similar molecular masses (38-42 kD) and shared between 50% and 85% of amino acids. All contained a hydrophobic signal sequence, and comparative analysis revealed 83 absolutely conserved amino acid residues, including 21 cysteines. WNT6 was one of the related proteins.

Mutation and expression studies have implicated the WNT gene family in early de-

developmental decision making in vertebrates and flies. In a detailed comparative analysis, Parr et al. [15] used in situ hybridization of 8.0- to 9.5-day mouse embryos to characterize expression of all ten published WNT genes in the central nervous system (CNS) and limb buds. They observed that in the forelimb primordia, WNT-3/4/6/7b were expressed fairly uniformly throughout the limb ectoderm.

In developing mouse embryos, WNT6 is expressed panectodermally and in the somites, limb bud and reproductive system and in adult mice it is expressed in the mammary gland. Rankin et al. [16] isolated a partial genomic clone of human WNT6 and found it assigned to human chromosome band 2q35 via in situ hybridization.

Kirikoshi et al. [17] cloned and characterized human WNT10A and WNT6. It was observed that WNT6 encoded a 365-amino-acid polypeptide with N-terminal signal peptide, WNT core domain, and RGD motif; and was found to be clustered in the head-to-tail manner with an interval less than 7.0 kb in human chromosome 2q35 region. Among human WNT family, WNT6 was found to be most homologous to WNT1 (47.4% amino-acid identity). Further, the 2.0-kb WNT6 mRNA was coexpressed with WNT10A in placenta and adult spleen; and WNT10A and WNT6 were strongly coexpressed in SW480 (colorectal cancer). They observed that overexpression of WNT10A and WNT6 might play key roles in human carcinogenesis through activation of WNT- β -catenin-TCF signaling pathway.

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight

is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [18] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [19] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [19].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [20]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [21], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [18] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [18]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [22], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface us-

ing the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. WNT6 related synergies

Note - WNT6 was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores

by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2nd order combinations of WNT6 were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of WNT6 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t WNT6. CKS2 - WNT6 shows high ranking of 129 , 241 (linear) , 212 (rbf) , 219 (jansen); CCNB2 - WNT6 shows high ranking of 185 (laplace) , 196 (linear) , 197 (rbf) , 209 (jansen); CDCA5 - WNT6 shows high ranking of 151 (laplace) , 189 (linear) , 166 (rbf) , 189 (jansen); TROAP - WNT6 shows high ranking of 178 (laplace) , 251 (linear) , 120 , 160 (jansen); TK1 - WNT6 shows high ranking of 247 (laplace) , 253 (linear) , 239 (rbf) , 193 (jansen); BRIP1 - WNT6 shows high ranking of 226 (laplace) , 121 , 233 (rbf) , 178 (jansen); HJURP - WNT6 shows high ranking of 215 (laplace) , 219 (linear) , 217 (rbf) , 68; while TPX2 - WNT6 shows low ranking of 4 , 15 , 11 , 150; TOP2A - WNT6 shows low ranking of 97 , 191 , 178 , 45; SPC25 - WNT6 shows low ranking of 127 , 187 , 146 , 82; KIF4A - WNT6 shows low ranking of 23 , 7 , 9 , 74; NEK2 - WNT6 shows low ranking of 130 , 248 , 222 , 143; KIF18B - WNT6 shows low ranking of 187 , 117 , 192 , 88; and DEPDC1B - WNT6 shows low ranking of 50 , 34 , 64 , 37.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t WNT6 with WNT6 – > CKS2 / CCNB2 / CDCA5 / TROAP / TK1 / BRIP1 / HJURP.

3.1.2. WNT6 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by WNT6, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2nd order combinations with WNT6, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the WNT6 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS WNT6				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T WNT6				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - WNT6	129	241	212	219
TPX2 - WNT6	4	15	11	150
TOP2A - WNT6	97	191	178	45
CCNB2 - WNT6	185	196	197	209
CDCA5 - WNT6	151	189	166	189
TROAP - WNT6	178	251	120	160
TK1 - WNT6	247	253	239	193
BUB1B - WNT6	249	239	126	91
CENPF - WNT6	218	132	214	98
SPC25 - WNT6	127	187	146	82
KIF4A - WNT6	23	7	9	74
NEK2 - WNT6	130	248	222	143
KIF18B - WNT6	187	117	192	88
BRIP1 - WNT6	226	121	233	178
DEPDC1B - WNT6	50	34	64	37
HJURP - WNT6	215	219	217	68

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT6 VS Individual members.

Of these, transmembrane 131 like (TMEM131L), meiotic nuclear divisions 1 (MND1), endonuclease/exonuclease/phosphatase family domain containing 1 (EEPD1), prostate transmembrane protein, androgen induced 1 (PMEPA1), hypoxia inducible factor 3 subunit alpha (HIF3A), shugoshin 1 (SGO1), HIG1 hypoxia inducible domain family member 1B (HIGD1B), CD101 molecule (CD101), neuron navigator 1 (NAV1), nucleolar and spindle associated protein 1 (NUSAP1), kinetochore scaffold 1 (KNL1), centrosomal protein 55 (CEP55), solute carrier family 7 member 1 (SLC7A1), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 17 (ADAMTS17), TOPBP1 interacting checkpoint and replication regulator (TICRR), denticleless E3 ubiquitin protein ligase homolog (DTL), ankyrin repeat domain 31 (ANKRD31), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (CDKN2A), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 1 (SKA1), solute carrier family 13 member 3 (SLC13A3), cell division cycle 25C (CDC25C), S100 calcium binding protein A1

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t WNT6

CKS2	WNT6
CCNB2	WNT6
CDCA5	WNT6
TROAP	WNT6
TK1	WNT6
BRIP1	WNT6
HJURP	WNT6

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT6 and Individual members.

(S100A1), plexin domain containing 1 (PLXDC1), tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2 (TEDC2), ribosomal protein L22 like 1 (RPL22L1), melanotransferrin (MELTF), solute carrier family 29 member 4 (SLC29A4), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 3 (SKA3), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 1 (HACD1), PCNA clamp associated factor (PCLAF), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1 (CDT1), cytoskeleton associated protein 2 like (CKAP2L), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A regulatory beta subunit 3 (KCNA3), progesterin and adipoQ receptor family member 8 (PAQR8), establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 2 (ESCO2), ribonucleotide reductase regulatory subunit M2 (RRM2), membrane associated ring-CH-type finger 3 (MARCH3), exonuclease 1 (EXO1), carbohydrate sulfotransferase 2 (CHST2), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 C (UBE2C), mucin 20, cell surface associated (MUC20), zinc finger protein 114 (ZNF114), vomeronasal 1 receptor 1 (VN1R1), H2A clustered histone 6 (HIST1H2AC), H2B clustered histone 4 (HIST1H2BC), IZUMO1 receptor, JUNO (IZUMO1R), ERCC excision repair 6 like, spindle assembly checkpoint helicase (ERCC6L), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 4 (HACD4), FAM111 trypsin like peptidase B (FAM111B), X-ray repair cross complementing 2 (XRCC2), BLM RecQ like helicase (BLM), solute carrier family 22 member 20, pseudogene (SLC22A20P), protocadherin gamma subfamily A, 1 (PCDHGA1), spire type actin nucleation factor 2 (SPIRE2), microRNA 635 (MIR635), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2), PITX1 antisense RNA 1 (C5orf66), KMT2E antisense RNA 1 (LINC01004), deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 2 (DLEU2), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B1 pseudogene 2 (NDUFB1P2), small regulatory polypeptide of amino acid response (SPAAR), thioredoxin domain containing 5 (TXNDC5), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1948 (LINC01948), dynein axonemal heavy chain 10 opposite strand (DNAH10OS) and DND microRNA-mediated repression inhibitor 1 (DND1), were found to be recorded

as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of WNT6 with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t WNT6.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS WNT6									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T WNT6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
TMEM131L - WNT6	190	190	135	96	MND1 - WNT6	171	186	246	109
EEPDI - WNT6	234	169	219	120	PMEPA1 - WNT6	221	86	207	212
HIF3A - WNT6	214	172	198	84	SGO1 - WNT6	239	204	147	172
HIGD1B - WNT6	138	214	137	214	CD101 - WNT6	153	224	257	191
NAV1 - WNT6	158	254	185	211	NUSAP1 - WNT6	211	223	232	77
KNL1 - WNT6	242	235	243	128	CEP55 - WNT6	195	146	250	202
SLC7A1 - WNT6	150	232	221	81	ADAMTS17 - WNT6	198	226	253	63
TICRR - WNT6	236	166	209	183	DTL - WNT6	176	199	183	55
ANKRD31 - WNT6	145	229	205	43	CDCA5 - WNT6	151	189	166	189
CDKN2A - WNT6	166	178	194	138	SKA1 - WNT6	163	157	187	148
SLC13A3 - WNT6	160	183	109	159	CDC25C - WNT6	194	217	215	162
S100A1 - WNT6	240	171	184	51	PLXDC1 - WNT6	146	234	225	198
TEDC2 - WNT6	228	216	161	60	RPL22L1 - WNT6	224	236	228	180
MELTF - WNT6	205	170	236	127	SLC29A4 - WNT6	189	111	202	215
SKA3 - WNT6	181	156	169	146	HACD1 - WNT6	231	130	201	151
PCLAF - WNT6	230	161	174	56	CDT1 - WNT6	233	228	211	181
CKAP2L - WNT6	229	211	176	225	KCNAB3 - WNT6	258	256	151	73
ESCO2 - WNT6	227	240	204	129	PAQR8 - WNT6	188	176	240	205
RRM2 - WNT6	257	137	237	152	MARCH3 - WNT6	197	242	252	185
EXO1 - WNT6	193	125	242	176	CHST2 - WNT6	182	154	227	72
UBE2C - WNT6	213	221	149	107	MUC20 - WNT6	212	177	224	137
ZNF114 - WNT6	170	145	188	104	VN1R1 - WNT6	250	203	234	157
HIST1H2AC - WNT6	80	164	231	204	HIST1H2BC - WNT6	152	209	199	217
IZUMO1R - WNT6	179	207	72	247	ERCC6L - WNT6	165	201	164	196
HACD4 - WNT6	232	116	171	227	FAM111B - WNT6	255	230	165	141
XRCC2 - WNT6	149	227	208	125	BLM - WNT6	192	202	256	230
SLC22A20P - WNT6	186	126	175	144	PCDHGA1 - WNT6	167	192	179	190
SPIRE2 - WNT6	225	182	206	203	MIR635 - WNT6	219	198	136	167
TRIM59 - WNT6	237	185	191	224	RCN1P2 - WNT6	256	257	244	163
C5orf66 - WNT6	238	143	189	210	LINC01004 - WNT6	142	233	182	206
NDUFB1P2 - WNT6	217	210	143	112	SPAAR - WNT6	89	245	200	194
DLEU2 - WNT6	103	218	229	187	TXNDC5 - WNT6	245	155	238	140
LINC01948 - WNT6	180	249	193	229	DNAH10OS - WNT6	169	225	157	156
DND1 - WNT6	254	208	142	87					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT6 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t WNT6 with WNT6 – > TMEM131L / MND1 / EEPDI / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / SGO1 / HIGD1B / CD101 / NAV1 / NUSAP1 / KNL1 / CEP55 / SLC7A1 / ADAMTS17 / TICRR / DTL / ANKRD31 / CDCA5 / CDKN2A / SKA1 / SLC13A3 / CDC25C / S100A1 / PLXDC1 / TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / MELTF / SLC29A4 / SKA3 / HACD1 / PCLAF / CDT1 / CKAP2L / KCNAB3 / ESCO2 / PAQR8 / RRM2 / MARCH3 / EXO1 / CHST2 / UBE2C / MUC20 / ZNF114 / VN1R1 / HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / IZUMO1R / ERCC6L / HACD4 / FAM111B / XRCC2 / BLM / SLC22A20P / PCDHGA1 / SPIRE2 / MIR635 / TRIM59 / RCN1P2 / C5orf66

/LINC01004/NDUFB1P2/SPAAR/DLEU2/TXNDC5/LINC01948/DNAH10OS
/DND1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t WNT6	
TMEM131L / MND1 / EEPD1 / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / SGO1 ...	
HIGD1B / CD101 / NAV1 / NUSAP1 / KNL1 / CEP55 ...	
SLC7A1 / ADAMTS17 / TICRR / DTL / ANKRD31 / CDCA5 ...	
CDKN2A / SKA1 / SLC13A3 / CDC25C / S100A1 / PLXDC1 ...	
TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / MELTF / SLC29A4 / SKA3 / HACD1 ...	
PCLAF / CDT1 / CKAP2L / KCNAB3 / ESCO2 / PAQR8 / RRM2 ...	
MARCH3 / EXO1 / CHST2 / UBE2C / MUC20 / ZNF114 / VN1R1 ...	
HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / IZUMO1R / ERCC6L / HACD4 ...	
FAM111B / XRCC2 / BLM / SLC22A20P / PCDHGA1 / SPIRE2 ...	
MIR635 / TRIM59 / RCN1P2 / C5orf66 / LINC01004 / NDUFB1P2 ...	
SPAAR / DLEU2 / TXNDC5 / LINC01948 / DNAH10OS / DND1	WNT6

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT6 and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic WNT6 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of WNT6-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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